

Best Practice Guidelines for the DOI Registration of Research Outputs with DataCite

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Introduction

Metadata and the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) are essential for the implementation of the FAIR principles¹ for research data. Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability are relevant to all research data across all disciplines. Researchers, data curators, and infrastructures face the challenge of a lack of standardization in research data management and metadata management alike. While some disciplines have developed standards for formats, metadata, and exchange protocols, other disciplines, and their sub-communities are still facing the challenge of building up these standards and at the same time complying with the FAIR principles. This document introduces best practices in the metadata provision of research outputs using the DataCite Metadata Schema². The goal of this document is to complement the already comprehensive DataCite Metadata Schema by giving concise hands-on best practice guidance on specific metadata properties.

In the following, these guidelines provide some background information, general metadata best practices for researchers, data curators, and repository operators, as well as best practices for DOI registration.

Background

One important challenge in research data management is the lack of standardization of how research data are stored, described, and exchanged. Only a small number of communities have agreed on standard file formats, standard metadata, and standard protocols to exchange this information. The main reasons for this lack of standardization are the diversity of requirements which differ widely across communities, and the challenges of developing community standards. But solving this problem is critical for exploiting the full potential of research data management. The NFDI4Ing³ Seed Funds for the Base Services project addresses the need to enable and support the use of PIDs and metadata within NFDI4Ing as an essential

¹ Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. In *Scientific Data* (Vol. 3, Issue 1). Springer Science and Business Media LLC. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² <http://schema.datacite.org>

³ <https://nfdi4ing.de>

component for the implementation of the FAIR principles for research data. The following guidelines are not restricted to the engineering sciences but serve as a template for other domains.

These best practice guidelines are primarily targeted at researchers, data curators, and repository operating institutions. These guidelines seek to support the efforts of metadata creators and curators to provide complete, consistent, and standardized metadata, making their research outputs FAIR. To reduce the time and resource-consuming burden of metadata creation and curation, the following guidelines give advice to each of the target groups on how to improve metadata curation workflow.

General metadata best practices for researchers, data curators, and infrastructures

How relevant are metadata for scholarly communication?

The key to making research outputs findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable is equipping datasets with metadata—descriptions of facts and figures about the data—that meets basic standards and adheres to a uniform, consistent schema. Even though it is obvious that more metadata better describes a research result, creating more metadata means more work at the same time. Therefore the effort of metadata creation has to be distributed between researchers, data curators, and infrastructures and automated wherever possible. The goal of metadata is to describe things in a manner that humans and machines are able to understand the object described. To this end, metadata has to be concise and unambiguous, as well as use terms and vocabularies that are widely accepted. Such use of standardized metadata is indispensable because research outputs and resources are integral parts of the research process and therefore need to be highly interoperable. The extent to which a research output or resource is described by metadata depends on the scope of the metadata, the research domain, and the character of the object itself.

Researchers

- Provide as much information and documentation about the described research output as possible, as this increases its visibility and impact.

Data curators

- Make researchers aware of the importance of metadata for the visibility and impact of their research through education (e.g. online courses and webinars), and information materials (e.g. support pages and handouts).
- Assist researchers with the creation of metadata wherever possible.

Infrastructures

- Build systems that make metadata creation easy for researchers and data curators. This includes integrating APIs for ingest of metadata from external sources to enrich or auto-suggest (e.g. subject classifications or affiliations) metadata in the submission form.

What is the use of a metadata schema?

A metadata schema sets the boundaries of description by defining which metadata is relevant for describing the object. The DataCite Metadata Schema “is a list of core metadata properties chosen for accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes, with recommended use instructions in the documentation.”⁴ The DataCite Metadata Schema is a global domain-agnostic standard that can be linked to other domain-specific metadata standards (e.g. schemas and ontologies) which allow more detailed descriptions of the resources described.

Researchers

- If you are aware of domain-specific metadata standards, then link them to global standards like the domain-agnostic DataCite Metadata Schema. (See related Identifier section below.)

⁴ DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2021). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.4. DataCite e.V. <https://doi.org/10.14454/3w3z-sa82>

Data curators

- Adhere to global metadata standards like the global domain-agnostic DataCite Metadata Schema as well as domain-specific or national metadata schemas relevant to the researcher.
- Use controlled vocabularies wherever possible.
- Researchers do not need to be concerned with metadata schema compliance but should be aware that finding research data is made easier by more complete metadata (see How relevant are metadata for scholarly communication?).

Infrastructures

- Build systems that comply with metadata standards, whether general, domain-specific, or national. Usually global (open source) software platforms from service providers enable compliance better with metadata standards than developing a system in-house.

Why are persistent identifiers important?

PIDs are essential for the persistent and unique identification of analog and digital objects in scholarly communication. As global standards, PIDs disambiguate objects, support linking between objects, and enable interoperability between systems. All of these characteristics foster the FAIRness of research outputs thus increasing the visibility and impact of research. Using PIDs saves researchers, data curators, and infrastructures alike a significant amount of time and resources.⁵ Without PIDs, reliable and permanent citation of objects is impossible.

Researchers

- When describing your research outputs, use PIDs (like DOIs) whenever possible, as they guarantee global and unique identification of the output making your research FAIR.
- Get an ORCID iD⁶ and use it throughout the research life cycle⁷.

⁵ Brown, Josh, Jones, Phill, Meadows, Alice, & Murphy, Fiona. (2022). Incentives to invest in identifiers: A cost-benefit analysis of persistent identifiers in Australian research systems. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7100578>

⁶ <https://orcid.org>

⁷ <https://resources.morebrains.coop/pidcycle/>

Data curators

- When describing research outputs and linking objects use PIDs whenever possible.
- Make researchers aware of the importance of PIDs for the visibility and impact of their research through education (e.g. online courses and webinars), and information materials (e.g. support pages and handouts).
- Assist researchers with the creation of PIDs (e.g. ORCID iDs and DOIs) wherever possible.

Infrastructures

- Build systems that integrate with open scholarly infrastructures like DataCite, ORCID, and ROR. Use their APIs to push and pull PID metadata to facilitate metadata creation, curation, and connection. Usually global (open source) software platforms from service providers enable API integration better than developing a system in-house.

What role do the FAIR principles play?

The FAIR principles⁸ of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability were created to improve scholarly communication throughout the research life cycle by strengthening machine-actionability to find and use research outputs automatically. The consistent use of PIDs when describing a resource guarantees the compliance with the FAIR principles.

Researchers

- Researchers do not necessarily need to know about the FAIR principles, yet should understand the importance of metadata completeness.

Data curators

- Data curators/stewards should have knowledge of the FAIR principles and foster them through metadata completeness.

⁸ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Infrastructures

- Infrastructures should build and use APIs to fetch and provide metadata that support reaching the goal of FAIRness through metadata completeness.
- Infrastructures should enable automated processing and reuse of metadata including the setup of quality assurance workflows.

Metadata best practice for the DOI registration of research outputs with DataCite

Metadata is important to the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research outputs (FAIR). The DataCite Metadata Schema supports this “FAIRness” by offering a comprehensive set of properties that are applicable to all domains. However, while there are only six required properties, more may be necessary in some contexts to provide key context information for their research community. The following metadata best practices for the DOI registration of research outputs give advice on how its metadata properties should be used to unleash the full potential of FAIRness.

When describing a resource, its relations to other entities and resources, to support its reusability, please follow the best practices below whenever possible:

- use persistent identifiers (PIDs)
- use controlled vocabularies based on international standards
- connect the resource to other entities and resources
- connect domain-specific metadata
- specify the language of the property used

Describing the resource

The following metadata properties describe the resource itself and should be used as follows:

Title

- Provide a main title that describes the resource as specific as possible.
- The main title should be the first title and omit the *titleType*.
- Specify the language of each title.
- Provide an English translation of the main title using *titleType* "TranslatedTitle".

Example

```
<titles>
  <title xml:lang="de">Fortschritte in der Chemie </title>
  <title xml:lang="en" titleType="TranslatedTitle">Advances in Chemistry</title>
  <title xml:lang="zh" titleType="TranslatedTitle">化学进展</title>
</titles>
```

Subject

- Although it is a recommended property, provide as much subject information (discipline and keywords) as possible—preferably using controlled vocabularies (e.g. classifications)—as this will improve findability across search engines and databases.
- Use the Fields of Science and Technology (FOS)⁹ classification to describe your resource.
- Use additional discipline-specific standards for more detailed descriptions of your resource.
- Provide an English translation of the keywords.

Example

```
<subjects>
  <subject schemeURI="http://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38235147.pdf" subjectScheme="Fields of Science and Technology (FOS)">FOS: Economics and business</subject>
</subjects/>
```

⁹ <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38235147.pdf>

Description

- Provide an abstract limited to 300 words.
- If you provide a non-English abstract, please provide also an English translation of the abstract.
- Specify the language of each description.

Example

```
<descriptions>
  <description xml:lang="de" descriptionType="Abstract">Beispiel Zusammenfassung</description>
  <description xml:lang="en" descriptionType="Abstract">Example abstract</description>
</descriptions>
```

Relationship between a resource and people and organizations

The following metadata properties describe the relationship between a resource and people and organizations and should be used as follows:

Creator

- Provide a PID such as ORCID iD for the *creator* of the resource or a ROR ID if the creator is an organization.
- Provide a ROR ID for the affiliation that the *creator* had when creating the resource.
 - If the *creator* has multiple affiliations, then provide them in the order of importance of the resource published.

Example

```
<creators>
  <creator>
    <creatorName nameType="Personal">Garcia, Sofia</creatorName>
    <givenName>Sofia</givenName>
    <familyName>Garcia</familyName>
    <nameIdentifier schemeURI="https://orcid.org/"
    nameIdentifierScheme="ORCID">0000-0001-5727-2427</nameIdentifier>
    <affiliation affiliationIdentifier="https://ror.org/03efmqc40"
    affiliationIdentifierScheme="ROR" schemeURI="https://ror.org">Arizona State
    University</affiliation>
  </creator>
</creators>
```

```
<creatorName xml:lang="en" nameType="Organizational">California Digital
Library</creatorName>
<nameIdentifier schemeURI="https://ror.org/"
nameIdentifierScheme="ROR">https://ror.org/03yrm5c26</nameIdentifier>
</creator>
</creators>
```

Contributor

- Provide a PID such as ORCID iD for the *contributor* of the resource or a ROR ID if the contributor is an organization.
- Provide a ROR ID for the affiliation information of the *contributor*.
- Select a *contributorType* for the Contributor.

Example

```
<contributors>
  <contributor contributorType="Data Collector">
    <contributorName nameType="Personal">Garcia, Sofia</contributorName>
    <givenName>Sofia</givenName>
    <familyName>Garcia</familyName>
    <nameIdentifier schemeURI="https://orcid.org/"
nameIdentifierScheme="ORCID">0000-0001-5727-2427</nameIdentifier>
    <affiliation affiliationIdentifier="https://ror.org/03efmqc40"
affiliationIdentifierScheme="ROR" schemeURI="https://ror.org">Arizona State
University</affiliation>
  </contributor>
  <contributor contributorType="HostingInstitution">
    <contributorName xml:lang="en" nameType="Organizational">California Digital
Library</contributorName>
    <nameIdentifier schemeURI="https://ror.org/"
nameIdentifierScheme="ROR">https://ror.org/03yrm5c26</nameIdentifier>
  </contributor>
</contributors>
```

Funder

- Provide a ROR ID for the *fundingReference* of a resource.

fundingReference example

```
<fundingReferences>
  <fundingReference>
    <funderName>European Commission</funderName>
    <funderIdentifier funderIdentifierType="Crossref Funder
ID">https://doi.org/10.13039/501100000780</funderIdentifier>
```

```
<awardNumber
awardURI="https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/100180_en.html">282625</awardNumber>
<awardTitle>Motivational strength of ecosystem services and alternative ways to
express the value of Biodiversity</awardTitle>
</fundingReference>
<fundingReference>
<funderName>European Commission</funderName>
<funderIdentifier funderIdentifierType="Crossref Funder
ID">https://doi.org/10.13039/501100000780</funderIdentifier>
<awardNumber
awardURI="https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/100603_en.html">284382</awardNumber>
<awardTitle>Institutionalizing global genetic-resource commons. Global Strategies
for accessing and using essential public knowledge assets in the life
sciences</awardTitle>
</fundingReference>
</fundingReferences>
```

Relationship with other resources

The following metadata properties describe the relationship between the resource and other resources and should be used as follows:

relatedIdentifier

- Provide relations like citations or references to other resources by using PIDs like DOIs in the *relatedIdentifier* property.
 - If possible, provide PIDs in the referenced resource that point back to the described resource.
- Provide domain-specific metadata using the *relationType* HasMetadata and the sub-properties *relatedMetadataSchema*, *schemeURI*, and *schemeType*.
- If you want to point to a software that was used to create the resource, use the *relationType* Requires.
- If you want to point to an instrument that was used to create the resource, use the *relationType* IsCompiledBy.

Example¹⁰

```
<relatedIdentifiers>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsCitedBy"
resourceTypeGeneral="JournalArticle">10.21384/bar</relatedIdentifier>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL" relationType="HasMetadata"
relatedMetadataScheme="DDI-L" schemeType="XSD"
schemeURI="http://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Lifecycle/3.1/XMLSchema/instance.xsd">
https://example.com/</relatedIdentifier>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsCompiledBy"
resourceTypeGeneral="Instrument">10.5072/instrument</relatedIdentifier>
</relatedIdentifiers>
```

Reusability

The following metadata properties describe the reusability of the resource and should be used as follows:

Rights

- Provide the license under which the resource was licensed using the Software Package Data Exchange License List (SPDX).
 - In general, provide only one license for the research output.

Example

```
<rightsList>
  <rights xml:lang="en" schemeURI="https://spdx.org/licenses/" rightsIdentifierScheme="SPDX"
rightsIdentifier="CC-BY-4.0" rightsURI="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/">Creative
Commons Attribution 4.0 International</rights>
</rightsList>
```

¹⁰ A new relationType for pointing to an instrument is under consideration for the DataCite Metadata Schema 4.5.

Additional reading

Burger, Marleen, Anette Cordts, und Ted Habermann. 2021. „Wie FAIR Sind Unsere Metadaten? : Eine Analyse Der Metadaten in Den Repositorien Des TIB-DOI-Services“. Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement, Nr. 3 (Dezember). German:1-13.

<https://doi.org/10.17192/bfdm.2021.3.8351>.

Faniel, I. M., Frank, R. D., & Yakel, E. (2019). Context from the data reuser's point of view. *Journal of Documentation*, 75(6), 1274–1297.

<https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-08-2018-0133>

Habermann, T. (2019, September 27). MetaDIG recommendations for FAIR DataCite metadata. <https://doi.org/10.5438/2CHG-B074>

Koshoffer, A., Neeser, A. E., Newman, L., & Johnston, L. R. (2018). Giving Datasets Context: A Comparison Study of Institutional Repositories that Apply Varying Degrees of Curation. *International Journal of Digital Curation*, 13(1), Article 1.

<https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v13i1.632>

Kümmet, Sonja, Lücke, Stephan, Schulz, Julian, Spenger, Martin, & Weber, Tobias. (2019). DataCite Best Practice Guide (Version 1.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3559800>

Kümmet, S., Lücke, S., Schulz, J., Spenger, M., & Weber, T. (2020). Standardizing a Standard: Why and how a Best Practice Guide for the DataCite Metadata Schema was created. IT-Gruppe Geisteswissenschaften (ITG), Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München.

https://doi.org/10.24344/KIT_POST_51272_1

Park, M. S., & Park, H. (2019). An examination of metadata practices for research data reuse: Characteristics and predictive probability of metadata elements. *Malaysian Journal of Library & Information Science*, 24(3), 61–75.

<https://doi.org/10.22452/mjlis.vol24no3.4>